
Implementation of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) In Uzbekistan

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the analysis of the process of implementation of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) in Uzbekistan. The key stages of reforms aimed at harmonizing national accounting standards with international requirements are considered. The advantages of the transition to IFRS for enterprises and the national economy, including increasing the transparency of financial reporting and improving the investment climate, are highlighted. qualified personnel and high costs for infrastructure adaptation. Based on the study, recommendations are proposed to minimize costs and improve the efficiency of IFRS implementation.

Key words: IFRS, accounting, Uzbekistan, financial statements, investment attractiveness, reforms, harmonization of standards.

INTRODUCTION

In today's globalization and internationalization of financial markets and economies, the importance of transparent and standardized financial reporting is constantly growing. The adoption of International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) has become a key milestone for many countries seeking to integrate into the global economic community.

Reforming accounting and financial reporting in Uzbekistan creates a foundation for strengthening investor confidence and attracting investment. With the adoption of IFRS, the national accounting system should demonstrate transparency, reliability and comparability with world standards.

For Uzbekistan, which is actively seeking to strengthen its presence in international markets, the transition to IFRS is becoming an urgent task. In 2020, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted a resolution "On additional measures for the transition to international financial reporting standards", providing for the gradual harmonization of national standards with international financial reporting principles.

This article is devoted to the analysis of the stages of accounting reform in Uzbekistan, the consideration of key challenges and problems related to the implementation of IFRS, and ways to solve them. The study will describe the positive effects of the reform, as well as formulate recommendations for the further development of accounting in accordance with the requirements of the digital economy.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The implementation of International Financial Reporting Standards is widely discussed in the works of both domestic and foreign researchers. Among the key works analyzing the impact of IFRS on the economy and accounting are the studies of Ahmed et al. (2013), which conducted a meta-analysis of the effects of IFRS implementation and pointed to their positive impact on the transparency and quality of financial statements [3].

Poleshchuk T.A. in his work "International Financial Reporting Standards: Problems of Implementation" emphasizes the importance of rethinking the criteria for the formation of accounting information in countries with transition economies. It focuses on the need to unify national standards to achieve greater comparability of reporting [4].

A study by B. Al-Shammari et al. (2018) highlights the role of the quality of compliance with standards, which can vary significantly between different jurisdictions [5]. These findings are supported by evidence of an increased role for disclosure in companies that have implemented IFRS.

The works of Zaripova S.Z. analyze the stages of integration of accounting in Uzbekistan with the application of IFRS. The author highlights the key differences between national and international standards and gives recommendations for overcoming existing barriers [6].

Important conclusions are also presented in the studies of Daske and Gebhardt (2006), who note that the transition to IFRS in European countries has contributed to the improvement of the quality of accounting and the strengthening of investor confidence [7].

Thus, a review of the literature demonstrates that the successful implementation of IFRS requires not only the adaptation of standards, but also significant efforts to train personnel, develop infrastructure and eliminate institutional barriers. This is confirmed by the results of studies indicating the need for an integrated approach to accounting reform.

METHODS

The methodological basis of the study is a systematic approach, which made it possible to analyze the stages of accounting reform in Uzbekistan and their relationship with international practice. Comparative analysis methods were used to study the differences between national accounting standards and IFRS, as well as analysis and synthesis methods to identify key problems and ways to solve them. The sources of data were regulatory legal acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan, statistical reports, as well as the results of research by domestic and foreign authors. Particular attention was paid to the study of the impact of the implementation of IFRS on the transparency and investment attractiveness of Uzbek companies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The main stages of reforms in Uzbekistan related to the implementation of IFRS began with the adoption of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No PP-4611 dated February 24, 2020 [2]. This document became the basis for the transition of large enterprises, such as joint-stock companies, commercial banks and insurance companies, to the mandatory application of international standards. In 2021, a phased implementation of reforms began, including the development of accounting policies, training of IFRS specialists and adaptation of information systems for reporting.

The key point was the introduction of mandatory disclosure of financial information in accordance with the requirements of IFRS. This step ensured greater transparency of reporting, which in turn strengthened investor confidence and increased the investment attractiveness of Uzbek companies. One of the important aspects of the reform was the creation of training centers, which made it possible to significantly improve the qualifications of specialists.

However, the reform process was accompanied by a number of challenges. Among them are the high cost of adapting IT systems, the lack of qualified personnel and the complexity of converting data from national standards to the IFRS format. An important stage was also the adoption of the Law "On Accounting" in a new edition, which came into force in 2024 and laid the foundation for further harmonization of national accounting with international standards.

The benefits of adopting IFRS for businesses are increased transparency of financial reporting, which strengthens investor confidence and improves access to international capital markets. Uzbek companies that meet international standards are becoming more competitive, which

contributes to an increase in foreign direct investment. In addition, the implementation of IFRS contributes to the improvement of corporate governance through better analysis and decision-making.

The national economy also faces challenges in the transition to IFRS. Among them are the insufficient development of the institutional infrastructure and the need to improve the legislative framework. However, long-term benefits, such as integration into the global economy and increased investment attractiveness, make the transition to IFRS strategically important for Uzbekistan.

Recommendations for minimizing costs and improving implementation efficiency:

Development of a state support program. Creating subsidies or tax incentives for businesses adopting IFRS will help reduce the financial burden, especially for small and medium-sized enterprises.

Large-scale training of personnel. The organization of national training programs and certification courses for accountants with an emphasis on the practical application of IFRS will eliminate the shortage of qualified specialists.

Adaptation of IT infrastructure. The development of standard software solutions compatible with IFRS will significantly reduce the cost of technical modernization for enterprises.

Creation of reference materials in Uzbek and Russian languages. The publication of translations and guidance on the application of IFRS in an accessible form will help speed up the process of implementation of standards.

Increased institutional coordination. Strengthening interaction between government agencies, professional associations and educational institutions to ensure a coherent approach to reforms.

Effective consulting of companies. Organization of consulting centers to provide methodological assistance in adapting reporting and solving emerging problems.

CONCLUSION

The implementation of IFRS in Uzbekistan is a strategically important area that contributes to the country's integration into the world economy. Significant progress has been made in the course of the reforms, including increasing the transparency of financial reporting, strengthening investor confidence and creating conditions for attracting foreign investment. Efforts to harmonize national accounting standards with international requirements played a key role in these processes.

Despite the successes achieved, the implementation of reforms is accompanied by a number of challenges. The main problems include a shortage of qualified personnel, high costs for adapting IT infrastructure and difficulties in converting financial statements from national standards to IFRS format. Overcoming these challenges requires a comprehensive approach that includes the development of educational programmes, state support and institutional strengthening.

The advantages of implementing IFRS for Uzbek enterprises are obvious. This includes improving access to international capital markets, increasing investment attractiveness and strengthening competitive positions at the global level. In addition, the application of international standards contributes to the development of corporate governance by providing better analysis and decision-making at the organizational level.

For the national economy, the transition to IFRS opens up new prospects. Integration into the world financial system creates prerequisites for long-term economic growth, an increase in the inflow of foreign direct investment and the strengthening of the country's position in the international arena. Based on the analysis, recommendations were developed aimed at minimizing costs and improving the efficiency of IFRS implementation. Among them are the development of a state support program, the creation of reference materials in Uzbek and Russian, the adaptation of IT infrastructure and large-scale training of specialists.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the successful implementation of reforms in the field of accounting requires the coordination of efforts of all stakeholders – the state, business and educational institutions. Only in this case will Uzbekistan be able to fully unleash the potential of IFRS implementation and achieve its strategic goals.

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